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EnCycLEd

Enhancing Cybersecurity
Literacy in Education

Dissemination Kit & Dissemination Strategy V1.0

REACH Innovation

Version 1.0 (updated-M4)

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	5
1. ENCYCLED BRANDING & DISSEMINATION KIT	6
1.1 Branding embedding EnCycLEd’s Vision	6
1.2 LOGO	7
1.3 EnCycLEd Deliverable Template	9
1.4 EnCycLEd Presentation Template	10
1.5 EnCycLEd Meeting Minutes Template.....	11
1.6 EnCycLEd Certificate Template	13
2. ENCYCLED DISSEMINATION GOALS.....	14
3. ENCYCLED TARGET GROUPS	15
4. ENCYCLED DISSEMINATION CHANNELS	16
4.1 EnCycLEd Dissemination within the Website.....	17
4.2 EnCycLEd Dissemination within LinkedIn	19
4.3 EnCycLEd Dissemination within Facebook	20
4.4 EnCycLEd Dissemination within Instagram	20
4.5 EnCycLEd Dissemination within X (Twitter)	21
4.6 EnCycLEd Dissemination within the Project Platform	22
4.7 EnCycLEd Zenodo Community	23
4.8 EnCycLEd Dissemination via YouTube.....	24
5. ENCYCLED NETWORK BUILDING	24
5.1 Tool-Kit for Network Building	24
5.1.1 Project Website & Social Media Channels	24
5.1.2 Deliverables & Other Project Results Documentation	26
5.1.3 EnCycLEd Presentations & Press Release Material	26
5.1.4 EnCycLEd Newsletters, Poster, Banner & Leaflet	27
5.2 Improving Project Dissemination via Networking	29
6. ENCYCLED SUSTAINABLE DISSEMINATION STRATEGY	30
6.1 Dissemination Strategy Goals	31
7. RESULTS MONITORING FOR DISSEMINATION.....	33
7.1 Specific EnCycLEd WPs Results Monitoring for Dissemination	35
8. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY KPIS & TARGETS.....	38

CONCLUSIONS..... 40

REFERENCES..... 41

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Color Palette used for EnCycLEd Branding.....	6
Figure 2: Logo Symbol Option 1.	7
Figure 3: Logo Symbol Option 2 with slogan.	7
Figure 4: Logo Symbol Option 3.	8
Figure 5: Logo Symbol B&W with frame.	8
Figure 6: Example Logo Mark Option 1.....	8
Figure 7: Example Logo Mark Option 4.....	8
Figure 8: Example of the EnCycLEd Logomark Option 2 with slogan.....	9
Figure 9: Example of the EnCycLEd Deliverable Template initial pages.....	10
Figure 10: Cover slide of the EnCycLEd PowerPoint Presentation Template.	10
Figure 11: Template for EnCycLEd Meeting Minutes.....	12
Figure 12: Template for EnCycLEd Certificates.....	13
Figure 13: Screenshot of the EnCycLEd Website (Home upper view).	17
Figure 14: LinkedIn Account for EnCycLEd (Screenshot featuring the account profile).....	19
Figure 15: Facebook Account for EnCycLEd (Screenshot featuring the account profile). ...	20
Figure 16: Instagram Account for EnCycLEd (Screenshot featuring the account profile). ..	21
Figure 17: X (Twitter) Account for EnCycLEd (Screenshot featuring the account profile). .	22
Figure 18: EnCycLEd Platform linked-page for announcements within the project Website.23	
Figure 19: EnCycLEd LinkedIn Impressions Metrics in the period of Feb.-March, 2024.....	25
Figure 20: EnCycLEd LinkedIn Engagement Rate in the period of Feb.-March, 2024.....	26
Figure 21: Cover of the Template Option for EnCycLEd Newsletters (made in Canva.com).28	
Figure 22: EnCycLEd Dissemination Strategy Goals.	31
Figure 23: Dissemination Strategy as a nutshell.	32
Figure 24: EnCycLEd Dissemination & Networking Structure.	32
Figure 25: EnCycLEd Results Dissemination Calendar (2024-2026).	35
Figure 26: EnCycLEd Social Media Awareness Days.....	38

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1: EnCycLEd Project – Dissemination Channels.....	16
Table 2: KPIs / Followers-Targets for the EnCycLEd Social Media Channels.....	39

ABOUT THE PROJECT

The EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project aims to promote digital readiness in cybersecurity, resilience, and capacity-building in educational institutions. To achieve this, the project will promote cybersecurity literacy and awareness. It focuses on training students, schoolteachers and other teaching professions to develop key digital skills and competences.

Special focus is given to promoting interconnected educational systems in Europe with cybersecurity awareness and training at High Schools, Vocational Schools, as well as at university courses, especially the ones related to the formation of future teachers. The project results are planned to go beyond the project's educational partners, taking effect also via interactions with the vast existing network of associated institutions of the partners.

The EnCycLEd consortium benefits from the diverse and profound experience of higher education partners, professional schools and associations in the topic areas of cybersecurity and didactics. The project counts with cybersecurity expertise coming from European Universities (UIBK in Austria and HU in Germany) and from a cybersecurity association (UACS in Ukraine), supported by two other Universities (UoM in Greece and SET Univ. in Ukraine) to develop and test the training materials and school curricula. Two project partners (AC in Malta and REACH in Austria) will respectively cater for the development of the project's digital platform and the project's dissemination and network-building. EnCycLEd will devote main efforts on interacting and piloting its developments in cooperation with two European Schools (in Greece and in Austria) and with two Ukrainian educational institutions (a University dedicated to the formation of teachers and a Vocational School).

INTRODUCTION

The EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project (Nr. 2023-1-AT01-KA220-SCH-000166888) aims to promote digital readiness in cybersecurity, resilience and capacity-building in educational institutions. It focuses on promoting interconnected educational systems in Europe with cybersecurity awareness and training. Dissemination has a very important role on this project, as it is responsible for bringing awareness to the target groups.

The present document describes the adopted *Dissemination Strategy* for the EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project, based on the project's goals and using the Dissemination Kit being developed by REACH project partner, to fulfill the aims of the Work Package 5 (WP5) on "Project Dissemination and Community Building".

The "EnCycLEd Dissemination Strategy" documentation comprises the following main topics:

1. EnCycLEd Branding & Dissemination Kit.
2. EnCycLEd Dissemination Goals.
3. EnCycLEd Target Groups.
4. EnCycLEd Dissemination Channels.
5. EnCycLEd Network / Community Building.
6. EnCycLEd Sustainable Dissemination Strategy.
7. EnCycLEd Results Monitoring for Dissemination
8. EnCycLEd Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Targets.

1. ENCYCLED BRANDING & DISSEMINATION KIT

Based on the vision of the EnCycLEd project to promote digital readiness in cybersecurity, resilience, and capacity-building in educational institutions, REACH developed a compelling branding that reflects both the aims and target audience of the EnCycLEd Project.

First, a suitable color palette was chosen based on the connection of the project with the subjects: "Education" and "Cybersecurity". Secondly, a Logo was proposed for the project, and it was graphically finalized using the color palette matching the branding study. Finally, templates and the digital presence of the project have been developed, using the branding elements proposed.

1.1 Branding embedding EnCycLEd's Vision

The branding proposed for EnCycLEd is based on the target audience, the area of application, as well as on the project's name itself. The Logo was inspired by the name EnCycLEd, as it portrays digital cycles to be connected. The color palette proposed is composed of vivid tones that reflect the project's aims to involve Highschool students, as well as students from Vocational Schools and Universities. The final design of the Logo using the proposed palette of colors also embeds the "modern vibe" that matches the Cybersecurity scenario.

Color Palette

The EnCycLEd project branding concept uses the color palette shown in Figure 1, composed of the following tones: #02366b (dark blue); #05cdfd (light blue); #ff386c (red); #689bce (grey-blue); and #ff9a05 (orange).

Figure 1: Color Palette used for EnCycLEd Branding.

1.2 LOGO

The Logo was developed in two categories: 1. Logo Symbol (only the Logo and the project acronym); and 2. Logo Mark (including Logo, acronym, and project slogan).

REACH developed 20 different versions of the Logo, varying between the two categories, formats, and the colors selected for the project branding. The Logos are to be used by the Consortium Partners according to their appropriate application, at their own decision. Examples of some of the Logos per category can be found in the figures that follow. A more detailed explanation of the EnCycLEd branding decisions will be available in the "Brand Brief" document currently being produced by REACH [2].

All Logo options are available in the nextcloud-ionos EnCycLEd project repository, within the "Work Package 5" sub-folder "EnCycLEd Logos", with internal direct link: <https://nc-634251456587349983.nextcloud-ionos.com/index.php/f/1440>. Some of the Logo options are available to be copied in the website of the project, on the "Dissemination Kit" page within "Resources" (<http://www.encycled.eu/dissemination-kit/>).

Figure 2: Logo Symbol Option 1.

Figure 3: Logo Symbol Option 2 with slogan.

Figure 4: Logo Symbol Option 3.

Figure 5: Logo Symbol B&W with frame.

Figure 6: Example Logo Mark Option 1.

Figure 7: Example Logo Mark Option 4.

Figure 8: Example of the EnCycLEd Logomark Option 2 with slogan.

1.3 EnCycLEd Deliverable Template

Based on the EnCycLEd branding and on the usual contents needed in EU project reports as deliverables, REACH designed a Word template for elaborating the Work Packages reports and deliverables documentation related to the EnCycLEd project. The current document is an example of the application of the use of this template.

The Word deliverable template file has the extension “dotx” for templates, is named “**EnCycLEd Deliverable Template – Final Version - Corrected.dotx**”, and can be found in the nextcloud-ionos EnCycLEd project repository, within the “Work Package 5” sub-folder “EnCycLEd Templates” (internal direct link: <https://nc-634251456587349983.nextcloud-ionos.com/index.php/f/1781>). It is advisable that the document is used as a template and not directly as a “docx” format file.

The deliverable template can also be directly downloaded from the EnCycLEd project website, on the “Dissemination Kit” page within “Resources” (<http://www.encycled.eu/dissemination-kit/>).

Figure 9: Example of the EnCycLEd Deliverable Template initial pages.

1.4 EnCycLEd Presentation Template

REACH provides a Power Point template for creating presentations about the EnCycLEd Project, for internal meetings and for external presentations of the project’s results coming from EnCycLEd Work Packages’ developments.

Figure 10: Cover slide of the EnCycLEd PowerPoint Presentation Template.

The Power Point presentation template file has the extension “pptx”, is named **“EnCycLEd PowerPoint Template – Corrected – Final Version.pptx”**, and can be found in the nextcloud-ionos EnCycLEd project repository, within the “Work Package 5” sub-folder “EnCycLEd Templates” (internal direct link: <https://nc-634251456587349983.nextcloud-ionos.com/index.php/f/1781>).

The use of the presentation template for the project’s work packages’ progress presentations is very important to keep the project branding identity, with the required credits for the EU funding and the Erasmus+ project number. It is expected to be used by all Consortium partners when reporting about the EnCycLEd project in live or virtual presentations.

The presentation template can also be directly downloaded from the EnCycLEd project website, on the “Dissemination Kit” page within “Resources” (<http://www.encycled.eu/dissemination-kit/>).

1.5 EnCycLEd Meeting Minutes Template

REACH also designed a Word template for reporting the project meetings’ minutes produced by the EnCycLEd project consortium, whenever the WPs’ meetings take place. See Figure 11. The template can be adapted by the project partners, according to their reporting needs. The table registering the meeting information is supposed to be present only on page 1.

The Word deliverable template file has the extension “dotx” for templates, is named **“EnCycLEd Meeting Minutes_Template.dotx”**, and can be found in the nextcloud-ionos EnCycLEd project repository, within the “Work Package 5” sub-folder “EnCycLEd Templates” (internal direct link: <https://nc-634251456587349983.nextcloud-ionos.com/index.php/f/1781>). It is advisable that the document is used as a template and not directly as a “docx” format file. This template can also be directly downloaded from the EnCycLEd project website, on the “Dissemination Kit” page within “Resources” (<http://www.encycled.eu/dissemination-kit/>).

EnCycLEd – Enhancing Cybersecurity Literacy in Education 1

ENCYCLED MEETING MINUTES

Meeting Title: [Text]

	WP(s):	Organized by:	Date: DD/MM/YY
	Participants:		Start: XX:XX
			End: YY:YY

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Figure 11: Template for EnCycLED Meeting Minutes.

1.6 EnCycLEd Certificate Template

A Word template for Participants Certificates of organized project workshops and trainings is also available (Figure 12). The template can be duplicated and adapted by the project partners, according to the organized events and participant names.

Figure 12: Template for EnCycLEd Certificates.

The Word certificate template file is named “**EnCycLEd Certificate_Template.docx**”, and can be found in the nextcloud-ionos EnCycLEd project repository, within the “Work Package 5” sub-folder “EnCycLEd Templates” (internal direct link: <https://nc-634251456587349983.nextcloud-ionos.com/index.php/f/1781>). It can also be directly downloaded from the EnCycLEd project website, on the “Dissemination Kit” page within “Resources” (<http://www.encycled.eu/dissemination-kit/>).

2. ENCYCLED DISSEMINATION GOALS

The EnCycLEd activities that are relevant to the communication and dissemination of the project are dealt within the work package WP5, with the following general aims:

- Create awareness about the project and communicate the project activities, events, outcomes, results and achievements to its target groups, as well as to the widest possible audience.
- Target and engage specific audiences and stakeholders who will benefit from the information, results and outputs of the project in order to raise awareness regarding and promote digital readiness in cybersecurity.
- Develop, implement and monitor a multi-dimensional communication and dissemination strategy to enhance the visibility of the project.
- Share project results with partner organizations and wider communities and maximize their impact.
- Promote the possibility of transferring and building on the results of the project into existing, new and improved practices that could be integrated into the programs of the partner schools and universities as well as other schools and universities across Europe.

The project results have great potential to be exploited by various schools and universities. Thus, it contributes to raising awareness and building capacity in these institutions to teach about cybersecurity. This way, students will have the opportunity to navigate safe online. The wide dissemination of the project

results, following the general goals listed above, play a paramount role in the project, in order to maximize the impact of the EnCycLEd project via the exploitation of its results.

3. ENCYCLED TARGET GROUPS

The EnCycLEd project is concerned with the topic of “Cybersecurity”, which is usually linked to a high degree of expertise in IT. Therefore, it is understood in an excluding way: only those with such an expertise have the knowledge to defend themselves against cyber-attacks. This perspective sets the tone for dividing the universe of the target audience into two groups: (1) People with qualified knowledge about cybersecurity; and (2) People without or only a small amount of experience and theoretical knowledge. Although the first group is an important target group, regarding the education about how to teach about cybersecurity, the most important group is the second one. The EnCycLEd project mainly focuses on people that experience the topic cybersecurity from an excluding perspective, inviting them to believe they can also benefit from the potentialities of cybersecurity.

The main target groups of stakeholders, who can profit the developments of the EnCycLEd project, can be divided in the following categories:

1. Students at High Schools / Vocational schools.
2. Teachers and other teaching personnel in high schools and vocational schools.
3. Students of Universities / High-Education Institutions.
4. Universities and High-Education Institutions’ Professors and Faculty Members.
5. Universities and High-Education Institutions’ Students’ Communities.
6. Local & International Educational Communities and Networks.
7. Local & International IT Communities and Networks.
8. Local, Regional & International Community Members (General Public).
9. 3rd Sector Organizations at Local Level and at EU & International Levels.

10. EU & Erasmus+ related Networks, Communities and Initiatives.
11. EU & Erasmus+ related Projects & involved Partners.

All the target groups categories listed here are considered within the project's Dissemination Strategy. They might need different ways to have information-contents communicated to them, via the different dissemination channels of the project.

4. ENCYCLED DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

The Disseminations Channels available for the project include: the Project Website; the Social Media accounts defined for the project (in LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, X (Twitter), YouTube); as well as the platform Zenodo and the project Platform (developed by ASCEND Consulting). The channels listed in Table 1 are the main means for disseminating the project results and especially for bringing about public engagement with the EnCycLEd Project.

Channel / Social Media	Site / Account / Link
EnCycLEd Website	EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project Website http://www.encycled.eu/
LinkedIn	encycled-project https://www.linkedin.com/company/encycled-project/
X (Twitter)	@encycled_proj https://x.com/encycled_proj https://twitter.com/encycled_proj
Instagram	@encycled_project https://www.instagram.com/encycled.project
Facebook	@encycled.project https://www.facebook.com/encycled.project
Zenodo*	EnCycLEd Project Zenodo Open Science Community (*soon available at https://zenodo.org/)
YouTube*	EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project YouTube Channel (*soon available at https://www.youtube.com/)
EnCycLEd Platform*	EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project Platform (*soon available at go.encycled.eu)

Table 1: EnCycLEd Project – Dissemination Channels.

All EnCycLEd social media accounts are linked in the project's website and REACH, as the dissemination project partner, promotes the project via posts about its main objectives and about its partners, among other project's initial activities. All project partners and collaborators are expected to engage with and to disseminate the EnCycLEd social media accounts, as well as to animate other project interested collaborators to follow the accounts, so that EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project can gain better visibility, achieve awareness about its goals and ways to reach them, and in consequence grow its network for further exploitation of the project's results.

Following the planned schedule, REACH set-up and launched the social media accounts for EnCycLEd, as well as the project website in March 2024.

4.1 EnCycLEd Dissemination within the Website

The website of the EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project, implemented via the URL: <http://www.encycled.eu/>, aims at creating awareness about the content, activities and results of the project. Its scope is an audience as wide as possible, e.g.: project stakeholders, vocational schools, non-vocational schools, universities, students, general public.

Figure 13: Screenshot of the EnCycLEd Website (Home upper view).

The design of the website relies on the branding previously described. The website will be built with the web content management system WordPress and will be optimized for users of desktops, laptops, and mobile devices (tablets, phones), which goes hand in hand with students being part of the target audience.

The EnCycLEd Website Pages are defined via its Menu, as follows:

1. Landing Page – Home (<http://www.encycled.eu/>)

2. About the Project (<http://www.encycled.eu/project/>)

- 2.1. WP1 - Project Management
- 2.2. WP2 - Analysis and Development
- 2.3. WP3 - EnCycLEd Platform
- 2.4. WP4 - Piloting and Assessment
- 2.5. WP5 - Dissemination

3. Project Partners (<http://www.encycled.eu/partners/>)

- 3.1. Leopold-Franzens-Universität Innsbruck
- 3.2. University of Macedonia
- 3.3. Ruprecht-Karls-Universität Heidelberg
- 3.4. SET University
- 3.5. UACS
- 3.6. KVS
- 3.7. American Farm School
- 3.8. ASCEND Consulting
- 3.9. REACH Innovation

4. Resources (<http://www.encycled.eu/resources/>)

- 4.1. Dissemination Kit
- 4.2. Publications
- 4.3. Linked Resources

5. Platform (<http://www.encycled.eu/encycled-platform/>)

6. News (<http://www.encycled.eu/news/>)

7. Contact (<http://www.encycled.eu/contact/>)

- 7.1. Disclaimer

4.2 EnCycLEd Dissemination within LinkedIn

The LinkedIn account for the EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/encycled-project/>) aims at networking with stakeholders and the project partners so that the latter can communicate EnCycLEd's activities to their own networks.

Figure 14: LinkedIn Account for EnCycLEd (Screenshot featuring the account profile).

4.3 EnCycLEd Dissemination within Facebook

The EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project Facebook account (<https://www.facebook.com/encycled.project>) aims at communicating the EnCycLEd project to various target groups, particularly focusing on Erasmus+ Communities, University students and faculty members, and on stakeholders.

Figure 15: Facebook Account for EnCycLEd (Screenshot featuring the account profile).

4.4 EnCycLEd Dissemination within Instagram

The EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project Instagram account (<https://www.instagram.com/encycled.project>) aims at communicating in an informal language the EnCycLEd project to various target groups within the broadest audience possible, particularly focusing on students, university students, faculty members, and on stakeholders.

Figure 16: Instagram Account for EnCycLEd (Screenshot featuring the account profile).

4.5 EnCycLEd Dissemination within X (Twitter)

The X (Twitter) account for EnCycLEd (https://x.com/encycled_proj; https://twitter.com/encycled_proj) targets a broader audience, including

people who may have general interests in Erasmus+ projects, as well as in cybersecurity.

Figure 17: X (Twitter) Account for EnCycLEd (Screenshot featuring the account profile).

4.6 EnCycLEd Dissemination within the Project Platform

The EnCycLEd project platform is currently under development, within WP3 by project partner ASCEND Consulting. The platform will be available according to schedule via the sub-URL of the project website: go.encycled.eu. The EnCycLEd Platform will be an important channel for the dissemination of the project

results. Among other features, it will be linked in the project-website to provide secured networking capabilities.

The goal of the EnCycLEd platform is to improve cybersecurity education and awareness for students, teachers, and professionals. It aims to offer a secure, easy-to-access, and interactive online environment, enabling the exchange of knowledge and resources among people from various languages and cultures. To access the EnCycLEd platform go to go.encycled.eu:

The development of the platform in WP3, by partner ASCEND with contribution from the EnCycLEd Project Consortium, seeks to meet the rising demand for thorough Cybersecurity Skills and Knowledge in a Digital Age.

The primary expected result is the creation of an active learning Community that enhances digital resilience and cybersecurity awareness, equipping users with the necessary skills to safeguard themselves in the online world.

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Figure 18: EnCycLEd Platform linked-page for announcements within the project Website.

4.7 EnCycLEd Zenodo Community

A Zenodo Open Science Community will be established for the EnCycLEd project at the Zenodo platform (<https://zenodo.org/>). All public materials and documentation produced by the EnCycLEd project will be included in this community. The Zenodo account for EnCycLEd will be soon launched and updated with the already existing public deliverables of the project.

4.8 EnCycLEd Dissemination via YouTube

The EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project YouTube Channel will be soon available at <https://www.youtube.com/>, containing all the public dissemination animations and videos developed for the project. This channel will be extremely supportive for the dissemination of the project results, workshops, training-courses, as well as stakeholders events.

5. ENCYCLED NETWORK BUILDING

The “Network Building” of the project EnCycLEd happens in a straightforward way, with the Consortium Partners’ collaboration, with the use of all created dissemination materials (Dissemination Kit) and the available communication and dissemination channels.

5.1 Tool-Kit for Network Building

All Dissemination-Kit elements, which will be available on the website-page via the menu-command “Resources” (<http://www.encycled.eu/resources/>), together with the resource materials that will be available at the EnCycLEd Platform (go.encycled.eu), are fundamental for the dissemination and network community building of the project. In this section, more information about the dissemination tool-kit elements is presented.

5.1.1 Project Website & Social Media Channels

All Media Channels of the Dissemination-Kit, described in Section 4 previously, play a very important role to enable network building for the project (for detailed information see the sub-sections 4.1 to 4.8 of this document).

The effectivity of the Social Media accounts can be measured directly via the platforms themselves: Taking the LinkedIn EnCycLEd account as an example, its “Contents Highlights” can report how many “Impressions” were made in a

certain amount of time. These include number of page views, number of unique visitors, and custom-button-clicks.

Figure 19: EnCycLEd LinkedIn Impressions Metrics in the period of Feb.-March, 2024.

The illustrations on Figure 19 and Figure 20 show the LinkedIn “Contents Highlights” report metrics for „Impressions Metrics“ and for „Engagement Rate“ of the EnCycLEd account, for the launching period of February to March, 2024. They show the positive effect that the EnCycLEd project is already gaining with its initial awareness posts on the LinkedIn platform.

Figure 20: EnCycLEd LinkedIn Engagement Rate in the period of Feb.-March, 2024.

5.1.2 Deliverables & Other Project Results Documentation

Based on the EnCycLEd branding and on the usual contents needed in EU project reports as deliverables, REACH designed a Word template for elaborating the Work Packages reports/deliverables related to the EnCycLEd project. The current document is an example of the use of this template. The “EnCycLEd Deliverable Template” is available for download on the website page via the “Dissemination Kit” page within menu-command “Resources” (<http://www.encycled.eu/dissemination-kit/>), as described in section 1.3 of the current document. The use of the template for the publications of the project is also important to keep the project branding identity.

5.1.3 EnCycLEd Presentations & Press Release Material

REACH provides a Power Point template for creating presentations about the EnCycLEd Project, for internal meetings and for external presentations, including also press release material, about the project’s results coming from

EnCycLEd Work Packages' developments. The "EnCycLEd Presentation Template" is available for download on the website page via the "Dissemination Kit" page within menu-command "Resources" (<http://www.encycled.eu/dissemination-kit/>), as described in section 1.4 of the current document.

5.1.4 EnCycLEd Newsletters, Poster, Banner & Leaflet

Based on the same concept of EnCycLEd branding, REACH designed a template for developing the Newsletters of the EnCycLEd Project. The preliminary cover page designed in Canva for the Newsletter can be viewed in Figure 21. The Newsletter is planned to be distributed digitally and eventually for printing (if required).

The forthcoming EncycLEd Newsletters will be available for download (pdf formats) on the website page via the "Publications" page within menu-command "Resources" (<http://www.encycled.eu/publications/>).

All Newsletters will be disseminated in all digital channels of the EnCycLEd project. If needed, the Newsletters can also be sent via email to selected stakeholders. Printing will be also possible, in the case of distribution needs in face-to-face events.

A Poster for the project is planned to be designed by REACH for the project. It will have the format of an A1 page, to be printed with thick glossy paper, using the branding concept developed for the project. Also, a Banner in the format of Roll-up will be produced for the project. Both EnCycLEd Poster and Banner templates will be released among the partners soon.

A Leaflet for the project is also under development by REACH. It will have the format of an A4 page, with 3 columns in its landscape layout, to be printed double sided, using the branding concept developed for the project. The EnCycLEd Leaflet template will be released among the partners soon.

The forthcoming Newsletters, the Poster, the Banner, and the Leaflet for the EnCycLEd project are under elaboration and will be available for download (pdf formats) on the website page via the “Publications” page within menu-command “Resources” (<http://www.encycled.eu/publications/>).

Figure 21: Cover of the Template Option for EnCycLEd Newsletters (made in Canva.com).

5.2 Improving Project Dissemination via Networking

It is extremely important that All Project Partners get engaged with the project Dissemination and with its Community Network Building. For bringing this in practice, partners are guided by the project dissemination partner on how to communicate the project's results and activities in an effective way. Specifically, the "what, why, how" methodology shall be used: "What" stands for the activity or result to be communicated itself; "Why" explains its importance; and "How" lists the steps to follow to achieve impact with the communication.

Project partners shall remember that "Information is giving out and Communication is getting through". They shall also keep in mind the differences that there are between the terms and concepts of "Communication", "Dissemination" and "Exploitation" in a project: Communication stands for informing about projects and their results. Dissemination stands for describing and making results available for use to a broader audience. Finally, Exploitation is concerned with making use of the project results as much and as impactful as possible.

With the above in mind, all project partners shall make sure that the following aspects are being continuously prepared and performed during project lifetime:

- Get the work package dissemination material ready, along its development, and send it to the REACH for posting and post about it individually and/or using your institution's distribution channels.
- Engage with Posts of EnCycLEd Accounts (e.g.: Like, Comment, Replicate, Invite Contacts, Indicate/Recommend to others).
- Send the digital version of EnCycLEd Leaflet to your colleagues.
- Send the digital version of EnCycLEd Newsletter to your contacts!
- Prepare a note about EnCycLEd Project to publish on the local newspaper of your city, or on your School Annual Report!

- Find new EnCycLEd or cybersecurity related projects and initiatives to enhance our Network.
- Act and interact! THINK GLOBAL & ACT LOCAL today & everyday!

6. ENCYCLED SUSTAINABLE DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The Dissemination Strategy for the EnCycLEd is based on the project's overall goals, using the Dissemination Kit already deployed to fulfill the specific dissemination aims defined within WP5. As already presented, together with the dissemination channels, some templates for the EnCycLEd project were elaborated by REACH, to be used all through the project lifetime, when producing Work Packages' Deliverables, Power Point Presentations, and periodic project Newsletters.

The EnCycLEd Dissemination Strategy is to be followed throughout the project lifetime, including the following tasks and aims:

- Report and promote the results of all the project work packages (WPs).
- Outline the target groups that need to be reached.
- Define the dissemination channels and tools, as well as the responsibilities of partners and instructions for reporting the dissemination activities.
- Promote the project and its outcomes to relevant stakeholders and the general public.
- Raise awareness about the specific objectives of the project and how they will be achieved.
- Disseminate the project results to relevant stakeholders, target group members and decision makers.
- Ensure the sustainability of the project results even after the completion of the project.

6.1 Dissemination Strategy Goals

The specific goals of the dissemination strategy are described as follows:

Figure 22: EnCyclEd Dissemination Strategy Goals.

From the specific goals illustrated in Figure 22, the following actions are considered by the project:

- Create awareness of the project via strategic and planned ways through the partnerships.
- Publish the EncyclED results and successes as extensively as possible.
- Use Open Access as much as possible.
- Increase awareness of the project among external stakeholders and external organizations.
- Reach potential third-party users of the project's results and developed methods.
- Build a project Network & Community.
- Enhance profile and the reputation of the partners-organizations via implementing the project.
- Impact future activities of the partners and of other connected organizations and communities of practice.
- Enforce usage and application of content and results from the project, as widely as possible.

In summary, the WP5 on “Dissemination and Community Building” will manage the aspects mentioned previously, through the communication, dissemination of results, and network-structure building, with the expected interaction among partners and external stakeholders, sharing information, as illustrated in Figure 23 and in Figure 24 shown below.

Figure 23: Dissemination Strategy as a nutshell.

Figure 24: EnCycLEd Dissemination & Networking Structure.

The interaction among all project partners and the dissemination partner is intuitive, taking into consideration the available information about the project results, all the communication channels designated for the project, and the partners' individual activities and networking.

7. RESULTS MONITORING FOR DISSEMINATION

In general, the monitoring of the work packages (WPs) project results and deliverables for their subsequent dissemination among the target groups of stakeholders is a crucial aspect of the project, playing a significant role in ensuring project success and impact. While dissemination ensures that the project's impact is maximized and knowledge is shared, monitoring deliverables is essential for maintaining control, minimizing risks, and ensuring the project stays on course throughout its lifecycle. Together, these practices contribute to achieving project objectives and maintaining stakeholder confidence in the project team's capabilities. The importance of both aspects related to monitoring and dissemination, rely on some general key-factors:

- **Knowledge Sharing:** Dissemination allows the sharing of project outcomes, findings, and knowledge with stakeholders, contributing to the collective understanding of the subject matter.
- **Validation and Recognition:** Sharing results provides a platform for validation by the wider community or relevant stakeholders, reinforcing the credibility of the project. Recognition of achievements enhances the project team's reputation and may attract potential collaborators, funders, or partners for future endeavours.
- **Informed Decision-Making:** Stakeholders, including policymakers, industry professionals, and the general public, can make more informed decisions based on the insights and outcomes generated by the project.
- **Technology Transfer:** Projects often develop new technologies, methodologies, or best practices. Dissemination facilitates the transfer of these innovations to other projects, industries, or communities.

- **Maximizing Impact:** Effective dissemination increases the potential impact of the project by reaching a broader audience, thereby contributing to the project's overall success and the achievement of its objectives.
- **Public Engagement:** Dissemination engages the public and raises awareness about the project's goals, encouraging public interest and support for the initiative.
- **Policy Influence:** Project results can influence policy decisions when shared with policymakers, helping to shape regulations, guidelines, or practices in the relevant field.
- **Feedback and Improvement:** Stakeholder feedback obtained through dissemination channels provides valuable insights for the project team, aiding in refining methodologies, addressing concerns, and improving future iterations or related projects.
- **Project Control:** Monitoring deliverables ensures that the project stays on track and aligns with its original objectives, timelines, and budgetary constraints.
- **Risk Management:** Regular monitoring helps identify potential risks and issues associated with deliverables early in the project lifecycle, allowing for timely corrective actions.
- **Resource Optimization:** Efficient monitoring allows for the optimal allocation of resources, preventing bottlenecks and ensuring that resources are utilized effectively to achieve project milestones.
- **Stakeholder Confidence:** Consistent monitoring and timely delivery of high-quality deliverables build stakeholder confidence in the project team's ability to meet its commitments.
- **Adaptability to Change:** Monitoring facilitates the identification of changes in project requirements, scope, or external factors, enabling the project team to adapt and adjust plans as needed.

- **Quality Assurance:** Monitoring ensures that deliverables meet predefined quality standards, reducing the likelihood of defects, errors, or the need for extensive revisions.
- **Communication and Transparency:** Regular updates on deliverable status promote transparency within the project team and among stakeholders, fostering effective communication and collaboration.
- **End-User Satisfaction:** For projects with external clients, monitoring and delivering on commitments contribute to client satisfaction, potentially leading to positive references or future collaborations.

7.1 Specific EnCycLEd WPs Results Monitoring for Dissemination

REACH will control the deadlines for project results and contact the partners beforehand, so that dissemination posts are distributed as soon as the results are available. See the “Results Dissemination Calendar”, shown in Figure 25, used for this purpose.

Figure 25: EnCycLEd Results Dissemination Calendar (2024-2026).

Overall, REACH will monitor and manage the dissemination of the project results, interacting with the project partners and specifically with the work package leaders, by following the schedule of work packages' results stated in the Dissemination Calendar for EnCycLEd.

The participation of EnCycLEd project partners in the tasks of communicating and disseminating the project is fundamental for the achievement of the key factors listed above and for the success of the project's impact. Partners, together with the project's target groups and stakeholders can help the project achieve higher impact levels, via basic joint-efforts:

- 1) **Leveraging Diverse Cybersecurity and Educational Networks** to involve them in dissemination activities, allowing the project this way to connect with a wider and more varied audience.
- 2) **Enhancing Credibility** and legitimacy to the project, by endorsing and participating in appropriate (cybersecurity and educational specific) dissemination efforts, creating in this way strong trustworthiness and reliability of the project's results and findings.
- 3) **Targeting Specific Audiences and Insights**, related to Cybersecurity Literacy and Awareness in Education, so that the dissemination can tailor strategies to effectively reach and engage these target groups, also ensuring that the project's messages are well received.
- 4) **Multiplying Outreach Efforts**, via the implementation of multiplier events, at local, regional, and EU levels, for extending the project's visibility beyond what the core team could achieve independently. As a consequence, this will allow for feedback on local and regional knowledge and expertise about the subjects involved, coming from the existing communities.
- 5) **Facilitating Two-Way Communication** with valuable feedback on dissemination strategies, involving other Cybersecurity Awareness initiatives, ensuring they are effective and resonate with the intended audience.

6) **Expertise and Resource Sharing** to support dissemination activities within a collaborative approach among the EnCycLEd Consortium Partners, for enhancing the overall quality of the dissemination efforts.

7) **Sustaining Long-Term Impact** of the activities planned for EnCycLEd, ensuring that the partnerships and the impact of dissemination activities can extend beyond the project's duration, via continued sharing of project outcomes even after the project concludes.

8) **Increasing Engagement Levels and Building a Supportive Ecosystem** via active partners' engagement with their own networks, fostering a sense of community around the project, as well as via building an ecosystem of Highschools, Vocational Schools, Universities, Organizations, Communities, and Individuals that are interested in the project's success. This will foster a collaborative and mutually beneficial environment for the project dissemination.

As it can be observed, all those collaborative efforts from partners will bring diversity, resources, and expertise to the EnCycLEd dissemination process, ensuring that the project's messages are effectively communicated and that its outcomes are widely recognized, practiced, and appreciated.

Furthermore, the dissemination contents will be regularly monitored. Statistics analysis of social media accounts will also be conducted to evaluate the content's reaches, engagements, and followers. After the release of individual outcomes such as posts, tweets, newsletters, and podcasts, a qualitative evaluation will be done at standard regular intervals. To identify gaps or leverage points in the EnCycLEd project's dissemination activities, self-evaluation of the project will be continuously carried out.

To follow the "Social Media Trends" related to "Cybersecurity", REACH also maintains a "#Hashtag-Social Media Awareness Days Calendar", which is updated every year, including subjects that relates to important aspects for Cybersecurity, like "Data Privacy", "Safer Internet", among others.

Figure 26: EnCycLEd Social Media Awareness Days.

8. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY KPIS & TARGETS

The definition of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and their estimated target values related to the dissemination of the project will be detailed further in the next version of this document (to be available before Month 6).

Quantitative Indicators for defined targets will be considered for engagements with the project’s Social Media Accounts. Examples: Number of Followers (as in Table 2), Reactions, Engagements and Impressions. With the website, the indicators are: Number of Visitors and Views: Page views per month, Visits per month, Visits per page, and average duration of individual visits.

Table 2 illustrates realistic and achievable project targets for communication via the Social Media channels, as well as the targets of the proposal.

Table 2: KPIs / Followers-Targets for the EnCycLEd Social Media Channels.

Channels / KPIs	KPI Month 06	KPI Month 12	KPI Month 24	KPI Month 36
LinkedIn	40	100	200	300
Proposal estimation		200		
KPI Control / Achievement		Posts & Stories engagements, #hashtags, contact tagging & contact invitation from partners		
Facebook	40	80	180	250
Proposal estimation		300		
KPI Control / Achievement		Posts & Stories engagements, #hashtags, contact tagging & contact invitation from partners		
Instagram	40	80	150	200
Proposal estimation		100		
KPI Control / Achievement		Posts & Stories engagements, #hashtags & contact tagging		
X -Twitter	15	25	35	50
Proposal estimation		60		
KPI Control / Achievement		Tweets / Posts Engagements, #hashtags		

Currently, in Month 4 of the project (**status of 26/03/2024**), in relation of Social Media Account Followers, the status is the following:

- **LinkedIn: 8 Followers**
- **X (Twitter): 34 Followers**
- **Instagram: 11 Followers**
- **Facebook: 22 Followers**

CONCLUSIONS

This document described the preliminary Dissemination Strategy adopted for the EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project, using its Dissemination Kit material, and how the adopted strategy envisages to grow the project's network and to gain more visibility within the main defined target groups in a sustainable way.

The Dissemination Kit together with the Dissemination Strategy build-up a solid structure within the EnCycLEd Erasmus+ Project, to completely fulfil the aims of the Dissemination Work Package WP5, led by REACH, while also achieving major awareness and visibility milestones of the project. This is made possible via the following added values of both Dissemination Kit (DK) and Dissemination Strategy (DS):

- DK: The compelling and attractive EnCycLEd branding, including various Logo options, matching the values of both project and target audience.
- DK: The EnCycLEd website will reach out to the general public and providing the basis for clear project communication about its activities and outcomes.
- DK: The social media accounts within major platform-channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, X / Twitter, YouTube) will increase the chances for positive impacts of the project on different audiences, not only within Europe but also Worldwide.
- DK: The fit-for-purpose, practical and trendy templates for producing EnCycLEd developments' deliverables; presentations; and newsletters.
- DS: The network building with the partners' collaboration will attend the EnCycLEd general dissemination goals.
- DS: The carefully planned way to make the EnCycLEd project's awareness and dissemination for the various defined target groups, via the proper use of the all available toolkit of materials and dissemination channels, will include the project platform to be developed.
- DS: The sustainability of the defined "EnCycLEd Dissemination Strategy" is fit-for-purpose to achieve the WP5 goals, via and necessary key performance indicators (KPIs) and realistic targets to be detailed further.

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